

UNIVERSITAS GADJAH MADA
PUSAT STUDI PANGAN DAN GIZI

Alamat: Gedung PAU-UGM, Jalan Teknika Utara, Berek, Yogyakarta 55281, Telp./Fax. (0274) 589242 <http://cfns.ugm.ac.id>, E-mail: cfns@ugm.ac.id

LAPORAN HASIL UJI

(Analysis Certificate)

No.PSPG/363/X/2021

Nama Pelanggan : dr. Syifa Mustika, SpPD-KGEH
(Name of client)

Alamat dan Telpon Pelanggan : Universitas Brawijaya
(Address and phone of client)

Nama dan Bentuk Sampel : Feses tikus

Uji yang diminta : SCFA

(Analysis requested)

Hasil Uji :

(Analysis Result)

No	Kode/sampel	Hasil Analisa		
		Asam Asetat (mMol/gram)	Asam Propionat (mMol/gram)	Asam Butirat (mMol/gram)
1	HFHFD1	49,7	23,9	2,3
2	HFHFD2	66,95	43,45	3,4
3	HFHFD3	43,94	19,47	5,59
4	HFHFD4	48,25	23,65	5,15
5	HFHFD5	71,15	30,3	6,45
6	HFHFD6	55,75	35,25	2,05
7	HFHFD7	46,45	20,18	4,64
8	HF1	87,45	32,55	5,65
9	HF3	56,2	25,1	3,95
10	HF4	69,45	27,75	11,9
11	HF5	55,35	24,75	5,6
12	HF6	53,1	25,45	4,2
13	HF7	49,55	15,55	5,27
14	N1	76,15	28,9	9,6
15	N2	63,05	17,6	9,25
16	N3	70,25	19,75	5,55
17	N4	74,8	24,55	18,2
18	N5	66,4	23,3	13,15
19	N6	55,1	21,5	7,4
20	N7	59,25	13,35	10,8
21	WD1	71,9	27,2	8,9
22	WD2	116,94	53,53	18,47
23	WD3	72,35	34,4	5,75
24	WD4	57,94	16,06	4,31
25	WD5	51,06	20,94	8,35
26	WD6	72,7	35,3	5,5
27	WD7	34,35	20,4	1,05

Yogyakarta, 27 Oktober 2021

Public Service PSPG – UGM

Method

<Analytical Line 1>

[Injection Port SPL2]

Injection Mode : Split
Temperature : 240,0 C
Carrier Gas : He
Flow Control Mode : Pressure
Pressure : 18,9 kPa
Total Flow : 102,1 mL/min
Column Flow : 3,20 mL/min
Linear Velocity : 28,4 cm/sec
Purge Flow : 3,0 mL/min
Split Ratio : 30,0
High Pressure Injection : OFF
Carrier Gas Saver : OFF
Splitter Hold : OFF

[Column Oven]

Initial Temperature : 110,0 C
Equilibration Time : 3,0 min

=Column Oven Temperature Program=

Total Program Time	Rate(C/min)	Temperature(C)	Hold Time(min)	
6,56 min	-----	110,0	0,00	
	1	9,0	160,0	1,00

[Column Information]

Column Name : BP21
Serial Number : 054474
Film Thickness : 0,50 um
Column Length : 25,0 m
Inner Diameter : 0,53 mm ID
Column Max Temp : 240 C
Installation Date : 2020/09/02

[Detector Channel 1 FID1]

Temperature : 250,0 C
Signal Acquire : Yes
Sampling Rate : 40 msec
Stop Time : 6,56 min
Delay Time : 0,00 min
Subtract Detector : None
Makeup Gas : He
Makeup Flow : 30,0 mL/min
H2 Flow : 40,0 mL/min
Air Flow : 400,0 mL/min

[General]

< Ready Check Heat Unit >
Column Oven : Yes
SPL2 : Yes
FID1 : Yes
< Ready Check Detector (FTD) >
< Ready Check Baseline Drift >
FID1 : No
< Ready Check Injection Flow >
SPL2 Carrier : Yes
SPL2 Purge : Yes
< Ready Check Add. Flow >
< Ready Check Detector APC Flow >

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 11/10/2021 11.14.37
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : STD VFA 111021 1
 Sample ID : STD VFA 111021 1
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVIS TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\STD VFA 111021 10 1.gc

ogram STD VFA 111021 1 D:\PUBLIK SERVIS TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\STD VFA 111021 10 1.gc - C

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,706	29567	6877	10,000	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,362	70874	20686	10,000	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,590	112814	37661	10,000	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,162	109069	34348	10,000	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,555	156412	53556	10,000	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	130585	38627	10,000	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	7,150	129524	35468	10,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	7,779	87343	21549	10,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	9,756	22161	4307	10,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 12.22.59
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 1
 Sample ID : HFHFD 1
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERWISE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 1.gcd

Chromatogram HD 1 D:\PUBLIK SERWISE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 1.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,710	29377	7961	9.936	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,368	33848	10780	4.776	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	0,000	0	0	0.000	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,170	4988	1607	0.457	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,567	1368	447	0.087	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	3814	850	0.292	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0.000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0.000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0.000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 11.40.21
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 2
 Sample ID : HFHFD 2
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 2.gcd

Chromatogram HD 2 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 2.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,709	39585	10934	13,388	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,367	61572	18887	8,687	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,168	7460	2368	0,684	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,564	2249	711	0,144	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,325	2824	880	0,216	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 10.05.29
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 3
 Sample ID : HFHFD 3
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 3.gcd

Chromatogram HD 3 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 3.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,701	22075	6035	7,466	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,360	23428	7479	3,306	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,590	3017	963	0,267	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,162	10385	3413	0,952	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,558	5192	1676	0,332	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	3896	1112	0,298	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 10.26.58
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 4
 Sample ID : HFHFD 4
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 4.gcd

Chromatogram HD 4 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 4.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,705	28517	7607	9,645	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,362	33520	10581	4,730	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,593	1347	374	0,119	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,164	11262	3603	1,033	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,561	2183	661	0,140	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,319	2179	596	0,167	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 13.03.23
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 5
 Sample ID : HFHFD 5
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 5.gcd

Chromatogram HD 5 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 5.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,712	42080	11570	14,232	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,370	42922	13669	6,056	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,590	2982	684	0,264	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,173	14011	4574	1,285	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,571	2887	890	0,185	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,331	3151	809	0,241	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 10.55.55
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 6
 Sample ID : HFHFD 6
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 6.gcd

Chromatogram HD 6 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 6.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,707	32972	8420	11,151	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,364	49966	15897	7,050	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,166	4445	1431	0,408	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,563	1475	410	0,094	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,322	1147	298	0,088	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 14.39.06
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFHFD 7
 Sample ID : HFHFD 7
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 7.gcd

Chromatogram HD 7 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HD 7.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,719	15105	4012	5,109	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	15710	4858	2,217	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,179	5536	1802	0,508	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,555	3506	880	0,224	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,337	1553	371	0,119	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 11.07.56
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 1
 Sample ID : HFD 1
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 1.gcd

Chromatogram HF 1 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 1.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,705	51711	14038	17,489	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,364	46128	14244	6,508	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,594	5079	1615	0,450	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,166	12368	4106	1,134	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,564	7754	2510	0,496	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	8259	2014	0,632	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 15.11.32
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 3
 Sample ID : HFD 3
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 3.gcd

Chromatogram HF 3 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 3.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,717	33224	9120	11,237	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,375	35551	11236	5,016	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,606	1636	551	0,145	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,178	8665	2967	0,794	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,577	3430	976	0,219	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,338	2012	545	0,154	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 15.47.54
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 4
 Sample ID : HFD 4
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 4.gcd

Chromatogram HF 4 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 4.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,716	41067	11278	13,889	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,375	39299	12364	5,545	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,606	2030	718	0,180	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,178	25984	8492	2,382	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,577	4184	1351	0,267	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,338	4102	1111	0,314	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 13.49.13
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 5
 Sample ID : HFD 5
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 5.gcd

Chromatogram HF 5 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 5.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,719	32740	8629	11,073	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	35091	10777	4,951	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,607	1524	463	0,135	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,180	12171	3987	1,116	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,577	5690	1208	0,364	MMOL
6	valeric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 13.33.53
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 6
 Sample ID : HFD 6
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 6.gcd

Chromatogram HF 6 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 6.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,713	31403	8741	10,621	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,372	36089	11549	5,092	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,603	1776	600	0,157	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,175	9138	2714	0,838	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,574	2754	883	0,176	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,334	1297	405	0,099	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 15.36.27
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : HFD 7
 Sample ID : HFD 7
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 7.gcd

Chromatogram HF 7 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\HF 7.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,719	16112	4391	5,449	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	12151	3772	1,714	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,608	1731	518	0,153	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,180	6364	2078	0,583	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,578	3226	1007	0,206	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,340	2115	532	0,162	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 12.33.10
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N 1
 Sample ID : N 1
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 1.gcd

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,708	45042	12722	15,234	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,367	40982	13121	5,782	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,596	1927	686	0,171	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,169	20962	6970	1,922	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,568	4151	1276	0,265	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,327	2957	895	0,226	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 12.44.02
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N 2
 Sample ID : N 2
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 2.gcd

Chromatogram N 2 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 2.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,711	37294	10283	12,613	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,370	24970	7829	3,523	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,599	3164	1113	0,280	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,171	20165	6513	1,849	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,570	4564	1469	0,292	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,329	3948	965	0,302	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 11.19.38
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N 4
 Sample ID : N 4
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 4.gcd

Chromatogram N 4 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 4.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,707	44228	12199	14,958	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,365	34797	10984	4,910	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,594	2561	742	0,227	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,166	39716	13176	3,641	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,563	3253	1029	0,208	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,324	3110	1008	0,238	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 14.53.23
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N 6
 Sample ID : N 6
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 6.gcd

Chromatogram N 6 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 6.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,719	32592	8843	11,023	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	30448	9560	4,296	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,607	1163	416	0,103	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,180	16190	5320	1,484	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,577	2012	610	0,129	MMOL
6	valeric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 15.25.19
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N 7
 Sample ID : N 7
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 7.gcd

Chromatogram N 7 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N 7.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,718	35022	9627	11,845	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	18909	5833	2,668	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,606	2538	887	0,225	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,179	23605	7678	2,164	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,579	8329	1663	0,533	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,339	2210	639	0,169	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 10.15.40
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N3
 Sample ID : N3
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N3.gcd

Chromatogram N3 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N3.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,702	41543	11344	14,050	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,361	27972	8865	3,947	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,590	1493	467	0,132	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,163	12102	3627	1,110	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,559	1976	583	0,126	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	3390	888	0,260	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 10.39.17
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : N5
 Sample ID : N5
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N5.gcd

Chromatogram N5 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\N5.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,705	39270	10908	13,281	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,363	33013	10736	4,658	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,592	2101	724	0,186	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,164	28646	9435	2,626	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,564	3542	1089	0,226	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,318	7247	1612	0,555	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 12.11.08
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 1
 Sample ID : WD 1
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 1.gcd

Chromatogram WD 1 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 1.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,710	42519	11547	14,380	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,368	38578	12119	5,443	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,598	2828	1072	0,251	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,170	19445	6443	1,783	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,568	5163	1708	0,330	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,328	5817	1679	0,445	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 11.51.32
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 2
 Sample ID : WD 2
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 2.gcd

Chromatogram WD 2 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 2.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,708	58765	15843	19,875	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,366	64508	20369	9,102	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,596	4124	1456	0,366	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,169	34197	11229	3,135	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,567	7769	2357	0,497	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,325	7150	1784	0,548	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 14.11.39
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 3
 Sample ID : WD 3
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 3.gcd

Chromatogram WD 3 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 3.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,720	42770	11599	14,465	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,378	48783	15133	6,883	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,608	1471	496	0,130	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,181	12500	3981	1,146	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,579	2229	679	0,143	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,340	3181	931	0,244	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 13.59.58
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 4
 Sample ID : WD 4
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 4.gcd

Chromatogram WD 4 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 4.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,718	27421	7422	9,274	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,377	18242	5734	2,574	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,607	2169	723	0,192	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,180	7468	2445	0,685	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,579	3221	1031	0,206	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,342	1234	438	0,095	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 15.59.39
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 5
 Sample ID : WD 5
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 5.gcd

Chromatogram WD 5 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 5.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,717	25668	6958	8,681	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,376	25247	7867	3,562	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,605	3020	1043	0,268	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,178	15458	5068	1,417	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,576	4734	1511	0,303	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,337	3041	905	0,233	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 14.23.23
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 6
 Sample ID : WD 6
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 6.gcd

Chromatogram WD 6 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 6.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret.Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,717	42979	11772	14,536	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,376	50044	15841	7,061	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,606	1813	606	0,161	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,179	11971	3808	1,098	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,577	4074	1298	0,260	MMOL
6	valeric acid	6,338	2125	687	0,163	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL

SHIMADZU GC SOLUTION ANALYSIS REPORT

Sample Information

Analysis Date & Time : 18/10/2021 13.16.56
 User Name : Admin
 Vial# : 1
 Sample Name : WD 7
 Sample ID : WD 7
 Data Name : D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 7.gcd

Chromatogram WD 7 D:\PUBLIK SERVICE TPHP\BP21\2021\452_PS_10_21\WD 7.gcd - Channel 1

Quantitative Results - Channel 1

ID#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Units
1	acetic acid	3,715	20320	5630	6,873	MMOL
2	propionic acid	4,373	28911	9163	4,079	MMOL
3	isobutyric acid	4,602	1066	391	0,095	MMOL
4	butyric acid	5,176	2288	734	0,210	MMOL
5	isovaleric acid	5,572	2459	693	0,157	MMOL
6	valeric acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
7	isocaproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
8	caproic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL
9	heptanoic acid	0,000	0	0	0,000	MMOL